

Concept: Binary encoding of the path followed by a filament in a network using DNA and decoding the trajectory with nanopore technology.

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To solve the encoding problem we use as a reference the network that encodes the subset sum problem [1]. This is a network that contains levels and intersections. When a filament faces an intersection, it can only opt for one of the two available paths; so we decided to use a binary system to encode the path that the filament is following. In addition, since the network is composed of hierarchical levels, the encoding can be made –and further read- in a sequential way.

The general idea is to write zeros and ones using DNA strands. The writing mechanism will be consecutive self-limiting strand displacement reactions [2] perform within the channels, and the numbering will be encoded in the height (topography) of DNA segments. With these features it would be possible to read the information encoded in the filament using a nanopore [3] sensor which will allow us to measure the changes in ionic current.

Encoding system

As in a Turing machine, our memory tape will be a long segment of single stranded DNA (ssDNA) and the cells will be equivalent to short segments of ssDNA (blue segments in Fig.1a) which are complementary to the long ssDNA segment (brown segment in Fig.1a). The shape of the blue segments is so that they are stabilized with their neighbors; that means that the outermost segment (the one located at the right edge) will be stabilized by only one neighbor. For this reason, there is a higher probability that the outermost segment would undergo a strand displacement reaction.

Since the network has a pyramid-like structure we were able to identify decision points (intersections) at each level (Fig. 1b). When the filament encounters an intersection it can go to the left or it can go to the right. Either of the paths that the filament can follow will trigger a strand displacement reaction (write a 1 for left and write a 0 for right) within the channel. The incoming strands (red or orange segments in Fig. 1c) will be hairpin structures [4] with different heights depending on the path that the filaments followed (short hairpin for right and tall hairpin for left). The incoming hairpin structures should be available in the channels; all of the left paths will have tall hairpins (1) and all of the right paths will have short hairpins (0); this can be achieved by functionalizing the corresponding channels with the hairpin structures or by giving an external supply¹.

¹ See example in Figure 1.

Once the outermost segment is replaced with the corresponding hairpin, the subsequent segment (corresponding to level 2) will now be stabilized by only one neighbor and it will be ready to start a strand displacement reaction (Fig.1a-l₂). These reactions will continue until the filament reaches the end of the network.

Figure 1. DNA-based writing mechanism. a) Consecutive self-limiting displacement of short low-affinity ssDNA (blue) by high-affinity hairpin structures (red and orange). The outermost low-affinity segment has the higher probability of being displaced. b) Schematic representation of the trajectory of the filament along the network (green line). c) Representation of the expected structures over the long ssDNA at the end of the network: $h_1 \rightarrow \text{left}=1$, $h_2 \rightarrow \text{left}=1$, $h_3 \rightarrow \text{right}=0$, $h_4 \rightarrow \text{left}=1$, end. Note: the drawing is not to scale and is for illustrative purposes only.

Readout system

Now that the filaments have reached the end of the network, it is time to decode their trajectory information. The sensing mechanism that we propose is inspired by the well-known nanopore sensing technology [3]. When a filament goes through the nanopore, the area that is available for the ions to travel changes and, with that, we can expect a change in the ionic current passing through the nanopore. The different sizes in the hairpins will produce different current signals (Fig. 2). With this we can read out sequentially the ones and zeros that were written during the filament trajectory. The sensor should be located at the end of the network and, depending on the required throughput, one or more sensors can be placed. It is important to mention that the output signal given by this technique is electrical, which is a suitable feature for further electronic integration.

Figure 2. Nanopore readout system. Schematic representation of a filament passing through a nanopore; the change of the effective area blocking the nanopore will result in a change in the ionic current. In this case, the graph is showing the expected “1-1-0-1” readout for this specific arrangement of tags. Note: the drawing is not to scale and is for illustrative purposes only.

In conclusion, we proposed a concept of encoding the trajectory of a filament in a complex network using DNA structures to write a binary tag in the filament. This information would be read using the nanopore technology. If this system is able to achieve good resolution it would be able to detect more than just high and low values. With this, it will be possible to use networks with multiple-choice intersections (not only bifurcations) which will allow us to extend the numerical system to more than just the binary system. As an option to achieve a good resolution another type of tags (nanoparticles or charged molecules) can be used to modify the conductivity when the filament goes through the nanopore. For characterization of the nanopore system, techniques such as AFM (hairpin topography) and electrophoresis can be used to verify the output results of the nanopore.

References:

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